

Dyslexia-associated protein (KIAA0319) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : KIAA0319 is a Dyslexia associated protein. It is implicated in developmental dyslexia, formation of the cerebral neocortex and specific language impairment, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue :** Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution :** In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of KIAA0319, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: KIAA0319, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

^{*}ML dicoveries of KIAA0319 synergy in Meningiomas

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Meningioma	2
1.1.1	World Health Organization (WHO) classification	2
1.1.2	Historical perspective	3
1.1.3	Pathophysiology	3
1.2	Dyslexia-associated protein (KIAA0319)	4
1.3	Roles of KIAA0319 in different disease	4
1.4	Insight behind the work	5
1.5	Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	6
2	Methods	6
2.1	Static data from Patel et al. [1]	6
2.2	Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	7
2.3	Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	8
2.4	Regarding biological insight	8
3	Results & Discussion	9
3.1	KIAA0319 related synergies	9
3.1.1	KIAA0319 - individual genes	9
4	Conclusion	11

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Dyslexia-associated protein (KIAA0319)

In this series of projects of sequencing human cDNA clones which correspond to relatively long transcripts, Nagase et al. [13] determined the entire sequences of 100 cDNA clones and the cDNA libraries used were the fractions with average insert sizes from 5.3 to 7.0 kb of the size-fractionated cDNA libraries from human brain. Of the 11, KIAA genes that were expressed in brain, KIAA0319 (Accession number - AB002317 & open reading frame (ORF) length - 1,072) was one of them.

1.3. Roles of KIAA0319 in different disease

Linkage between **developmental dyslexia (DD)** and chromosome 6p had been replicated in a number of independent samples and attempts to identify the gene respon-

sible for the linkage had produced inconsistent evidence for association of DD with a number of genes in a 575-kb region of chromosome 6p22.2, including VMP, DCDC2, KIAA0319, TTRAP, and THEM2. Cope et al. [14] aimed to identify the specific gene or genes involved by performing a systematic, high-density (approximately 2-3-kb intervals) linkage disequilibrium screen of these genes in an independent sample, incorporating family-based and case-control designs in which dyslexia was defined as an extreme representation of reading disability. They first observed evidence for association with 17 single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), 13 of which were located in the KIAA0319 gene. After redundant SNPs were excluded, 10 SNPs were individually genotyped in 223 subjects with DD and 273 controls. Six SNPs showed significant evidence of association in both samples, including a SNP (rs4504469) in exon 4 of the KIAA0319 gene that changes an amino acid. Their data strongly suggested that KIAA0319 was a susceptibility gene for dyslexia.

After identifying a risk haplotype associated with dyslexia on chromosome 6p22.2 which spanned the TTRAP gene and portions of THEM2 and KIAA0319, Paracchini et al. [15] showed that in the presence of the risk haplotype, the expression of the KIAA0319 gene was reduced but the expression of the other two genes remains unaffected. They further detected a very distinct expression pattern of the KIAA0319 gene in the developing cerebral neocortex of mouse and human fetuses, using in situ hybridization. Their data pointed to a direct link between a specific genetic background and a biological mechanism leading to the development of dyslexia, i.e the risk haplotype on chromosome 6p22.2 down-regulated the KIAA0319 gene which was required for neuronal migration during the **formation of the cerebral neocortex**.

Rice et al. [16] analyzed genetic linkage and association of measures of language, speech and reading phenotypes to candidate regions in a single set of families ascertained for **specific language impairment** (SLI). They carried out Sib-pair and family-based analyses for candidate gene loci for Reading Disability (RD) on chromosomes 1p36, 3p12-q13, 6p22, and 15q21, and the speech-language candidate region on 7q31 in a sample of 322 participants ascertained for Specific Language Impairment (SLI). In particular, they observed that linkage analysis replicated the influence of genes on chromosome 6p for all three domains, but association analysis indicated that only one of the candidate genes for reading disability, KIAA0319, had a strong effect on language phenotypes. Their findings were consistent with a multiple gene model of the comorbidity between language impairments and reading disability and had implications for neurocognitive developmental models and maturational processes.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations,

across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [17] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [18] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [18].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as provid-

ing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [19]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [20], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [17] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [17]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [21], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here `rbf` for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. KIAA0319 related synergies

Note - KIAA0319 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2nd order combinations of KIAA0319 were recorded.

3.1.1. KIAA0319 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with KIAA0319 showed high rankings - neurite extension and migration factor (NEXMIF), oxysterol binding protein like 6 (OSBPL6), BMP and activin membrane bound inhibitor (BAMBI), transmembrane protein 54 (TMEM54), G protein signaling modulator 2 (GPSM2), coiled-coil domain containing 136 (CCDC136), afadin, adherens junction formation factor (AFDN), proline rich and Gla domain 4 (PRRG4), KLF transcription factor 4 (KLF4), FXYD domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXYD6), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2), epidermal growth factor (EGF), KIAA1644 (KIAA1644), kinesin family member 21A (KIF21A), PILR alpha associated neural protein (PIANP), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL), immunoglobulin like domain containing receptor 2 (ILDR2), cellular retinoic acid binding protein 2 (CRABP2), sushi domain containing 4 (SUSD4), HHIP like 2 (HHIPL2), thrombospondin type 1 domain containing 7B (THSD7B), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13 (GALNT13), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), glutamate decarboxylase like 1 (GADL1), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit beta2 (GABRB2), scavenger receptor cysteine rich family member with 4 domains (SSC4D), solute carrier family 26 member 7 (SLC26A7), lipocalin 2 (LCN2), cadherin 8 (CDH8), family with sequence similarity 124 member A (FAM124A), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 2 (ITIH2), chondrolectin (CHODL), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), F-box protein 32 (FBXO32), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3), nucleophosmin/nucleoplasmin 2 (NPM2), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6), actin alpha cardiac muscle 1 (ACTC1), C3 and PZP like alpha-2-macroglobulin domain containing 8 (CPAMD8), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 2 (SGPP2), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit gamma1 (GABRG1), carboxypeptidase A3 (CPA3), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 3 (ARHGEF3), neuropeptide Y receptor Y1 (NPY1R), hyperpolarization activated cyclic nucleotide gated potassium channel 1 (HCN1), defensin beta 1 (DEFB1), transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6), WNK lysine deficient protein kinase 2 (WNK2), aquaporin 3 (Gill blood group) (AQP3), solute carrier family 16 member 9 (SLC16A9), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), coiled-coil domain containing 68 (CCDC68), glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1 (GPD1), dynein axonemal as-

sembly factor 3 (DNAAF3), HRAS-like suppressor family, member 5 (HRASLS5), bradykinin receptor B2 (BDKRB2), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), kallikrein related peptidase 7 (KLK7), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 (PCSK9), mucin 3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), discs, large (*Drosophila*) homolog-associated protein 1 (DLGAP1), heparan sulfate 6-O-sulfotransferase 2 (HS6ST2), potassium two pore domain channel subfamily K member 3 (KCNK3), lysophosphatidic acid receptor 3 (LPAR3), angiotensin like 7 (ANGPTL7), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), trypsin alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), bisphosphoglycerate mutase (BPGM), cold shock domain containing C2 (CSDC2), synaptrophin gamma 2 (SNTG2), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), leucine rich repeat and Ig domain containing 2 (LINGO2), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), myosin ID (MYO1D), repressin, TP53 dependent G2 arrest mediator homolog (RPRM), transmembrane protein 125 (TMEM125), cadherin 4 (CDH4), transmembrane protein 30B (TMEM30B), receptor interacting serine/threonine kinase 4 (RIPK4), family with sequence similarity 162 member B (FAM162B), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member A3 (ALDH1A3), brain expressed X-linked 5 (BEX5), oxysterol binding protein 2 (OSBP2), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), RNA binding motif protein 11 (RBM11), limbic system associated membrane protein (LSAMP), potassium voltage-gated channel interacting protein 4 (KCNIP4), piccolo presynaptic cytomatrix protein (PCLO), NF2, moesin-ezrin-radixin like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2), metallophosphoesterase domain containing 1 (MPPED1), forkhead box I2 (FOXI2), keratin 16 (KRT16), pyroglutamylated RFamide peptide receptor (QRFP), phospholipase A2 group IIA (PLA2G2A), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4), trypsin beta 2 (TPSB2), aldo-keto reductase family 1 member B10 (AKR1B10), DDB1 and CUL4 associated factor 12 like 2 (DCAF12L2) and SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of KIAA0319 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t KIAA0319 with KIAA0319 → NEXMIF / OSBPL6 / BAMBI / TMEM54 / GPM2 / CCDC136 / AFDN / PRRG4 / KLF4 / FXYD6 / HECW2 / EGF / KIAA1644 / KIF21A / PIANP / COL2A1 / MDGA2 / MAEL / ILDR2 / CRABP2 / SUS4 / HHIPL2 / THSD7B / GALNT13 / ACKR3 / GADL1 / GABRB2 / SSC4D / SLC26A7 / LCN2 / CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / ITIH2 / CHODL / SLC26A2 / FBXO32 / GRHL3 / NPM2 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 / CPAMD8 / COX6B2 / CYP3A4 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / GABRG1 / CPA3 / ARHGEF3 / NPY1R / HCN1 / DEFB1 / TRPV6 / WNK2 / AQP3 / SLC16A9 / PPP1R36 / CCDC68 / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 / BDKRB2 / NSG1 / KLK7 / PCSK9 / MUC3A / DLGAP1 / HS6ST2 / KCNK3 / LPAR3 / ANGPTL7 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / BPGM / CSDC2 / SNTG2 / CES4A / LINGO2 / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / RPRM / TMEM125 / CDH4 / TMEM30B / RIPK4 / FAM162B / ALDH1A3 / BEX5 / OSBP2 / SDR42E1

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS KIAA0319									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T KIAA0319									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
NEXMIF - KIAA0319	154	167	211	64	OSBPL6 - KIAA0319	158	156	193	54
BAMBI - KIAA0319	182	110	201	299	TMEM54 - KIAA0319	159	247	157	295
GPSM2 - KIAA0319	257	155	290	103	CCDC136 - KIAA0319	203	91	264	290
AFDN - KIAA0319	169	194	288	96	PRRG4 - KIAA0319	277	126	196	291
KLF4 - KIAA0319	157	98	298	284	FXYD6 - KIAA0319	260	291	238	123
HECW2 - KIAA0319	187	183	186	129	EGF - KIAA0319	186	190	156	107
KIAA1644 - KIAA0319	198	227	161	270	KIF21A - KIAA0319	208	152	254	287
PIANP - KIAA0319	302	285	146	230	COL2A1 - KIAA0319	236	250	224	204
MDGA2 - KIAA0319	249	280	266	162	MAEL - KIAA0319	294	249	307	242
ILDR2 - KIAA0319	298	288	300	203	CRABP2 - KIAA0319	224	282	73	297
SUSD4 - KIAA0319	271	246	253	265	HHIPL2 - KIAA0319	150	272	181	199
THSD7B - KIAA0319	238	216	248	217	GALNT13 - KIAA0319	295	267	233	240
ACKR3 - KIAA0319	225	137	188	166	GADL1 - KIAA0319	307	237	297	163
GABRB2 - KIAA0319	231	289	255	192	SSC4D - KIAA0319	107	252	150	168
SLC26A7 - KIAA0319	285	232	271	234	LCN2 - KIAA0319	268	210	274	121
CDH8 - KIAA0319	223	231	261	115	FAM124A - KIAA0319	280	215	122	282
CCDC3 - KIAA0319	292	214	291	189	ITIH2 - KIAA0319	207	253	252	90
CHODL - KIAA0319	275	296	235	200	SLC26A2 - KIAA0319	259	284	217	119
FBXO32 - KIAA0319	279	212	205	227	GRHL3 - KIAA0319	191	271	189	134
NPM2 - KIAA0319	160	168	145	276	CLIC6 - KIAA0319	234	283	260	176
ACTC1 - KIAA0319	216	128	171	302	CPAMD8 - KIAA0319	227	277	184	191
COX6B2 - KIAA0319	287	287	302	232	CYP3A4 - KIAA0319	188	218	220	292
AKNAD1 - KIAA0319	282	240	295	197	SGPP2 - KIAA0319	258	303	306	269
GABRG1 - KIAA0319	248	278	228	243	CPA3 - KIAA0319	263	223	287	241
ARHGEF3 - KIAA0319	218	201	213	29	NPY1R - KIAA0319	305	305	272	195
HCN1 - KIAA0319	251	302	106	161	DEFB1 - KIAA0319	306	307	229	210
TRPV6 - KIAA0319	239	171	130	273	WNK2 - KIAA0319	289	263	268	222

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between KIAA0319 VS Individual members.

/ MAFF / RBM11 / LSAMP / KCNIP4 / PCLO / NF2 / MPPED1 / FOXI2 / KRT16 / QRFPR / PLA2G2A / FAM78B / FAM78B / FAT4 / TPSB2 / AKR1B10 / DCAF12L2 / SH3BGRL2.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic KIAA0319 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of KIAA0319-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS KIAA0319									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T KIAA0319									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
AQP3 - KIAA0319	281	206	257	198	SLC16A9 - KIAA0319	272	276	153	139
PPP1R36 - KIAA0319	197	191	66	275	CCDC68 - KIAA0319	267	241	273	173
GPD1 - KIAA0319	286	239	202	92	DNAAF3 - KIAA0319	222	256	164	136
HRASLS5 - KIAA0319	299	298	289	193	BDKRB2 - KIAA0319	226	258	203	223
NSG1 - KIAA0319	201	225	93	249	KLK7 - KIAA0319	290	260	292	205
PCSK9 - KIAA0319	269	257	285	239	MUC3A - KIAA0319	288	144	277	228
DLGAP1 - KIAA0319	278	182	230	148	HS6ST2 - KIAA0319	274	275	180	172
KCNK3 - KIAA0319	232	219	284	185	LPAR3 - KIAA0319	265	221	259	159
ANGPTL7 - KIAA0319	254	173	46	272	MBOAT1 - KIAA0319	242	209	152	102
TPSAB1 - KIAA0319	266	292	246	247	BPGM - KIAA0319	180	178	8	266
CSDC2 - KIAA0319	241	255	61	219	SNTG2 - KIAA0319	291	207	286	218
CES4A - KIAA0319	195	165	137	258	LINGO2 - KIAA0319	283	293	212	259
SLCO2A1 - KIAA0319	247	196	218	128	MYO1D - KIAA0319	233	184	214	188
RPRM - KIAA0319	293	300	276	236	TMEM125 - KIAA0319	244	261	267	160
CDH4 - KIAA0319	273	254	208	169	TMEM30B - KIAA0319	163	279	223	88
RIPK4 - KIAA0319	296	199	159	260	FAM162B - KIAA0319	255	234	237	209
ALDH1A3 - KIAA0319	152	266	206	122	BEX5 - KIAA0319	153	299	241	252
OSBP2 - KIAA0319	261	224	304	154	SDR42E1 - KIAA0319	253	228	278	246
MAFF - KIAA0319	205	176	154	245	RBM11 - KIAA0319	250	208	197	105
LSAMP - KIAA0319	270	294	155	253	KCNIP4 - KIAA0319	300	248	280	220
PCLO - KIAA0319	262	235	250	208	NF2 - KIAA0319	161	233	198	180
MPPED1 - KIAA0319	301	268	299	224	FOXI2 - KIAA0319	284	306	167	155
KRT16 - KIAA0319	297	297	275	248	QRFPR - KIAA0319	304	304	301	221
PLA2G2A - KIAA0319	264	295	210	225	FAM78B - KIAA0319	229	170	67	304
FAM78B - KIAA0319	229	170	67	304	FAT4 - KIAA0319	240	188	97	251
TPSB2 - KIAA0319	256	281	243	186	AKR1B10 - KIAA0319	303	286	279	238
DCAF12L2 - KIAA0319	228	301	305	256	SH3BGR2 - KIAA0319	171	274	76	289

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between KIAA0319 VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

References

- [1] A. J. Patel, Y.-W. Wan, R. Al-Ouran, J.-P. Revelli, M. F. Cardenas, M. Oneissi, L. Xi, A. Jalali, J. F. Magnotti, D. M. Muzny, et al., Molecular profiling pre-

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t KIAA0319	
NEXMIF / OSBPL6 / BAMBI / TMEM54 / GPSM2 ...	
CCDC136 / AFDN / PRRG4 / KLF4 / FXYD6 ...	
HECW2 / EGF / KIAA1644 / KIF21A / PIANP ...	
COL2A1 / MDGA2 / MAEL / ILDR2 / CRABP2 ...	
SUSD4 / HHIPL2 / THSD7B / GALNT13 / ACKR3 ...	
GADL1 / GABRB2 / SSC4D / SLC26A7 / LCN2 ...	
CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / ITIH2 / CHODL ...	
SLC26A2 / FBXO32 / GRHL3 / NPM2 / CLIC6 ...	
ACTC1 / CPAMD8 / COX6B2 / CYP3A4 / AKNAD1 ...	
SGPP2 / GABRG1 / CPA3 / ARHGEF3 / NPY1R ...	
HCN1 / DEFB1 / TRPV6 / WNK2 / AQP3 / SLC16A9 ...	
PPP1R36 / CCDC68 / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 ...	
BDKRB2 / NSG1 / KLK7 / PCSK9 / MUC3A / DLGAP1 ...	
HS6ST2 / KCNK3 / LPAR3 / ANGPTL7 / MBOAT1 ...	
TPSAB1 / BPGM / CSDC2 / SNTG2 / CES4A / LINGO2 ...	
SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / RPRM / TMEM125 / CDH4 ...	
TMEM30B / RIPK4 / FAM162B / ALDH1A3 / BEX5 ...	
OSBP2 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / RBM11 / LSAMP / KCNIP4 ...	
PCLO / NF2 / MPPED1 / FOXI2 / KRT16 / QRFPR ...	
PLA2G2A / FAM78B / FAM78B / FAT4 / TPSB2 ...	
AKR1B10 / DCAF12L2 / SH3BGRL2	KIAA0319

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between KIAA0319 and Individual members.

dicts meningioma recurrence and reveals loss of dream complex repression in aggressive tumors, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116 (2019) 21715–21726.

- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] D. N. Louis, A. Perry, P. Wesseling, D. J. Brat, I. A. Cree, D. Figarella-Branger, C. Hawkins, H. Ng, S. M. Pfister, G. Reifenberger, et al., The 2021 who classification of tumors of the central nervous system: a summary, *Neuro-oncology* 23 (2021) 1231–1251.
- [4] S. H. Torp, O. Solheim, A. J. Skjulsvik, The who 2021 classification of central nervous system tumours: a practical update on what neurosurgeons need to know a minireview, *Acta Neurochirurgica* 164 (2022) 2453–2464.

- [5] A. Czarnetzki, E. Schwaderer, C. M. Pusch, Fossil record of meningioma, *The Lancet* 362 (2003) 408.
- [6] D. O. Okonkwo, E. R. Laws Jr, Meningiomas: historical perspective, in: *Meningiomas*, Springer, 2009, pp. 3–10.
- [7] S. Paterniti, Meningiomas surgery in Italy in the nineteenth century: Historical review, *Austin Neurosurg Open Access* 2 (2015) 1030.
- [8] Z. Pecchioli, Soria di un fungo della dura madre, operato collestirpazione dal professor zanobi pecchioli, *Nuovo Giornale de'LetteratiScienze* 36 (1838) 39–44.
- [9] H. Cushing, The meningiomas (dural endotheliomas): their source, and favoured seats of origin, *Brain* 45 (1922) 282–316.
- [10] W. contributors, Meningioma — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, 2024. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Meningioma&oldid=1259055917>, online; accessed 11-April-2025.
- [11] M. N. Pamiir, P. M. Black, R. Fahlbusch, *Meningiomas : a comprehensive text*, Elsevier Health Sciences, 2010.
- [12] F. Szulzewsky, H. N. Thirimanne, E. C. Holland, Meningioma: current updates on genetics, classification, and mouse modeling, *Upsala Journal of Medical Sciences* 129 (2024) 10–48101.
- [13] T. Nagase, K.-i. Ishikawa, D. Nakajima, M. Ohira, N. Seki, N. Miyajima, A. Tanaka, H. Kotani, N. Nomura, O. Ohara, Prediction of the coding sequences of unidentified human genes. vii. the complete sequences of 100 new cDNA clones from brain which can code for large proteins in vitro, *DNA Research* 4 (1997) 141–150.
- [14] N. Cope, D. Harold, G. Hill, V. Moskvina, J. Stevenson, P. Holmans, M. J. Owen, M. C. ODonovan, J. Williams, Strong evidence that KIAA0319 on chromosome 6p is a susceptibility gene for developmental dyslexia, *The American Journal of Human Genetics* 76 (2005) 581–591.
- [15] S. Paracchini, A. Thomas, S. Castro, C. Lai, M. Paramasivam, Y. Wang, B. J. Keating, J. M. Taylor, D. F. Hacking, T. Scerri, et al., The chromosome 6p22 haplotype associated with dyslexia reduces the expression of KIAA0319, a novel gene involved in neuronal migration, *Human molecular genetics* 15 (2006) 1659–1666.
- [16] M. L. Rice, S. D. Smith, J. Gayán, Convergent genetic linkage and associations to language, speech and reading measures in families of probands with specific language impairment, *Journal of neurodevelopmental disorders* 1 (2009) 264–282.

- [17] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [18] G. Pujol, B. Iooss, A. Janon, K. Boumhaout, S. Da Veiga, J. Fruth, L. Gilquin, J. Guillaume, L. Le Gratiot, P. Lemaitre, et al., Sensitivity: global sensitivity analysis of model outputs, R package version 1 (2017).
- [19] H. Huang, Y. Liu, M. Yuan, J. Marron, Statistical significance of clustering using soft thresholding, *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* 24 (2015) 975–993.
- [20] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [21] R. C. Team, R language definition, Vienna, Austria: R foundation for statistical computing 3 (2000) 116.